

Fuzz ball defects in unidirectional carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profiles: Numerical compressive strength predictions

O.V. Ferguson^{1,2}, C. Kildegaard¹, J.B. Jørgensen¹ and L.P. Mikkelsen²

¹LM Wind Power, Kolding, Denmark.

²Department of Wind and Energy Systems, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, Denmark.

E-mail: olen@dtu.dk

Abstract. Manufacturing-induced defects in fibre-reinforced polymers are an inherent challenge in manufacturing large structures, making it essential to understand their impact on structural performance and to define acceptable defect tolerances. This work addresses the issue by developing a finite element framework to characterise the compressive behaviour of composites with fibre misalignment defects. The method is demonstrated using a unidirectional carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profile containing an embedded fuzz ball defect. Simulation results are validated against experimental four-point bending tests of sandwich beams. A compressive strength prediction model, closely resembling the experimental setup, was developed using realistic fibre distributions from micrographs and implementing them in a non-linear finite element model. All tested sandwich beams with fuzz ball defects exhibited compressive failure in the gauge section. Post-mortem microscopy revealed localised through-thickness kink band failure, which was used to identify a representative modelling plane for a 2D plane strain model. Predictions showed kink band failure in regions of severe fibre misalignments, consistent with experimental observations. The predicted compressive strain to failure was within 3% of the measured average. This 2D modelling approach demonstrates high accuracy in capturing the effects of manufacturing-induced defects and provides an efficient tool for assessing structural risks associated with fibre misalignment defects.

1 Introduction

Manufacturing deviations in fibre-reinforced polymers that cause changes to the fibre structure are considered one of the major root causes of compressive strength reductions in the wind turbine blade industry [1]. Wrinkles and other kinds of fibre waviness in continuous unidirectional composites are typical manufacturing-induced defects that strongly impair the compressive performance, and ultimately cause premature failure due to severe fibre misalignments relative to the main load direction [2]. Experimental efforts to characterise the compressive strength of carbon fibre composites used in spar cap designs demonstrate the sensitivity to fibre misalignments. Wilhelmsson et al. [3] investigated a Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) with a maximum through-thickness fibre misalignment ranging from $\approx 4^\circ$ to 8° , and demonstrated a compressive strength reduction from 750 MPa to 400 MPa, respectively. Similarly, Davidson and Waas [4] presented a compression test of thick carbon fibre laminates with embedded wrinkles and showed compressive strengths down to 200 MPa.

Fibre misalignments in carbon fabric-based composites challenged the manufacturing of spar caps with strict quality requirements and control. Alternative carbon fibre products, like pultruded profiles, were introduced into the spar cap design to improve the stiffness- and strength-to-mass ratio with blade mass reductions up to 31% demonstrated by Ennis et al. [5] for a 72 m blade. The pultrusion process offers high consistency and quality, producing fixed cross-section components with a high fibre volume fraction and low degree of fibre misalignments [6]. Jeppesen et al. [7] investigated the difference in

fibre orientation distributions for a conventional NCF and pultruded profile, where they demonstrate a significant difference in the through-thickness fibre orientation, with a standard deviation of 4.5° for the NCF and 1.2° for the pultruded profile. The lower degree of fibre misalignments and higher fibre volume fraction in pultruded profiles result in higher compressive strengths close to 1200 MPa for a low-cost heavy-tow carbon fibre profile [5].

Characterising the detrimental effect of manufacturing-induced defects requires extensive and complicated experimental work and is limited to the envelope of the tested defects. Due to the significant variability in defect types and size, there is an incentive to create an analytical or numerical framework for predicting the compressive behaviour based on realistic fibre distributions. In continuation of the experimental work presented by Wilhelmsson et al. [3] and Davidson and Waas [4], meso-scale Finite Element (FE) models were developed to replicate the compression test of the pristine NCF and wrinkle case, respectively. Both modelling approaches are based on observations from realistic fibre distributions. Davidson et al. [4] considered a parametrised and idealised wrinkle case, while Wilhelmsson et al. [8] determined a realistic fibre distribution for a pristine NCF, using an image processing method that extracts local fibre orientations from micrographs. As presented by Ferguson et al. [9], manufacturing-induced defects in pultruded profiles, like the fuzz ball defect, cause severe through-thickness fibre misalignments. The fuzz ball defect is considered a foreign object consisting of broken fibres accumulating into a ball, and subsequently dragged into the pultrusion die. The defect affects the fibre distribution locally, resulting in complex fibre misalignments with no possibility for simplifying the fibre structure into amplitude and wavelength, as is usually assumed for laminate wrinkles. Compressive strength prediction tools, like the one presented by Wilhelmsson et al. [8], are thus required to capture a realistic fibre distribution, ultimately causing premature compressive failure.

This work aims to develop a numerical framework for compressive strength predictions of unidirectional fibre-reinforced polymers with manufacturing-induced defects, based on case-specific fibre distributions. The numerical framework is demonstrated for a case study on predicting the compressive strength of a carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profile with an embedded Artificial Fuzz Ball Defect (AFBD), and is based on experimental observations presented by Ferguson et al. [9]. There, the compressive strain to failure is characterised using a sandwich beam design in a four-point bending test setup, where localised compressive failure was observed in the vicinity of the defect, with through-thickness kink band failure.

Compressive strength predictions are based on a FE framework developed by Ferguson et al. [10], capable of predicting the compressive behaviour from realistic fibre distributions determined using X-ray computed tomography or optical microscopy data. Fibre distributions are represented with local fibre volume fractions and fibre orientation distributions derived from the image data, where the embedded defect imposes significant through-thickness fibre redistributions. The fibre distributions are imported into a FE-model resembling the four-point bending setup of a sandwich beam, where compressive failure is associated with kink band failure and captured using a non-linear constitutive material model developed by Christoffersen and Myhre Jensen [11].

2 Material and manufacturing-induced defect

The current numerical study is based on experimental results and observations presented in [9], which was performed on a Unidirectional (UD) Carbon Fibre-reinforced Pultruded Profile (UDCFPP). The UDCFPP is manufactured using the pultrusion process, where dry carbon fibre rovings are guided through a fixed cross-section pultrusion die with integrated resin infusion and curing [6]. The pristine material is presented in Figure 1a and is intended for the manufacture of spar caps in wind turbine blades, by stacking the UDCFPPs to meet the stiffness and strength requirements.

The manufacturing-induced defect investigated in [9] is known as a fuzz ball defect that initially appears as a ball of dry, entangled carbon fibres. The dry fuzz ball is generated from loose or broken fibres in the guided pultrusion system, where friction points cause loose fibres to accumulate into balls. If not removed from the system, the dry fuzz balls risk being dragged into the curing die and, ultimately, embedded in the UDCFPP. To investigate the detrimental effects of manufacturing-induced defects on the materials' compressive strength, a series of UDCFPPs with Artificial Fuzz Ball Defects (AFBDs) were manufactured as presented in [9].

Figure 1: Unidirectional Carbon Fibre-reinforced Pultruded Profile, UDCFPP.

An embedded AFBD is presented in Figure 1b together with lines indicating the cuts used for optical microscopy. As explained in [9], compressive failure initiates from a region outside the boundary of the visible defect, corresponding to line Z1 in Figure 1b. A micrograph from this region is thus used to benchmark a FE-model capable of predicting compressive strength based on fibre distributions estimated from micrographs.

3 Experimental characterisation of compressive failure

A pure compression test of thick UDCFPPs with large embedded defects will require long and wide compression test specimens with a high risk of failure due to asymmetry introduced by the defect. Instead, the compressive strain to failure was characterised for the UDCFPP with AFBDs in [9] using the sandwich beam design and four-point bending test setup presented in Figure 2. The beam design was inspired by the work of Wu and Wisnom [12], where they successfully tested a carbon fibre prepreg to compressive failure in the gauge section while ensuring that the failure strain was insensitive to through-thickness stress gradient effects.

The beam design presented in Figure 2 consists of UDCFPP face sheets and a polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) core, where the PMMA was chosen due to its high shear strength of 62 MPa, to mitigate the risk of core failure. Six beams with embedded AFBDs were manufactured, with the defect tested on the compression side in the four-point bending test setup. Five reference beams with pristine UDCFPP face sheets were compared with the AFBD samples.

Figure 2: Sandwich beam with UDCFPP face sheets and PMMA core used in a four-point bending test setup. Strain gauges are placed on the tension and compression sides.

Table 1: Test matrix and sandwich beam dimensions according to Figure 2.

Beam type	Number of samples [-]	Core thickness [mm]	Beam width [mm]	Beam length [mm]	Support span [mm]	Load span [mm]
Pristine	5	15	40	920	875	84
AFBD	(3, 3)*	15	(40, 60)*	620	590	84

* Refers to two beam configurations with three samples having a width of 40 mm and another three samples with a width of 60 mm.

The six AFBD beams comprised two design configurations to investigate potential test artefacts. However, all beams yielded similar results and were ultimately combined in the comparison with the pristine reference beams. For a detailed description of the different design configurations and sandwich beam manufacturing, the reader is referred to [9]. All beam dimensions are presented in Table 1, where the pristine beams are designed with a longer support span to increase the maximum strain capacity while reducing indentation loads from the load rollers.

Far field strain was measured on all beams using 3 mm single strain gauges (HBM 1-LY11-3/350) on the tension and compression sides on the face sheets as presented in Figure 2. The strain gauge position relative to the defect and the load rollers was approximately 20 mm, and with 5 mm to the edge of the face sheets.

4 Compressive strength prediction method

The compressive behaviour of a UDCFPP with an embedded AFBD is simulated using the image-based FE-model presented in [10], for predicting the compressive strength of unidirectional fibre-reinforced polymers based on realistic fibre distributions quantified from 2D or 3D imaging modalities. The choice of modelling strategy is based on experimental observations from [9], where it was concluded that compressive failure is associated with localised kink band formation of fibres adjacent to the visible defect at the cross-section Z1 in Figure 1b. Through-thickness kink band failure was observed and coupled with large fibre misalignments of unidirectional fibres surrounding the defect.

Due to the predominant through-thickness failure characteristics, it is argued that the simple 2D micrograph modelling approach is appropriate for predicting compressive failure confined to a predetermined through-thickness failure plane. The following subsection summarises the method presented in [10], and presents the estimated field quantities used as input for the FE-model.

4.1 Image acquisition and processing

The 2D micrograph approach is based on Large Field of View (LFOV) images acquired using optical microscopy. The cross-sections in Figure 1b were prepared using the grinding and polishing procedure presented in [9]. LFOV images were generated from a mesh of 8×72 overlapping micrographs with a 20% overlap, resulting in a 120.000×10.000 pixel image with a pixel size of $0.58 \mu\text{m}$. The resulting LFOV images are presented in Figure 3, and used for determining the fibre orientation and fibre volume fraction distribution, later used in the FE-model. The supplementary image at cross-section Z2 in Figure 3b, is used for comparison with the observed failure plane in Z1 to investigate competing failure planes.

Through-thickness fibre orientations, ϕ_{xy} , are estimated using the image processing method, structure tensor method, following the 2D version of the Python package [7], *structure-tensor*. Predominant orientations in the image are based on the gradient information along the axes, where the contrast between constituents governs the quality of the output fibre orientation distribution. The method is summarised for the pristine UDCFPP material in [10], while a detailed presentation of the method is provided in [13], with a demonstration for a NCF.

The estimated fibre orientation distribution for cross-section Z1 is presented in Figure 4 for the left half of the image. The distribution within the embedded AFBD is random, with fibres moving in and out of the image plane. Estimated orientations within the boundary of the defect are thus random, with large through-thickness orientations attributed to fibres directed out-of-images. As these orientations are artefacts of the 2D approach and do not resemble realistic distributions, a mask is assigned to the defect area to define material parameters different from the unidirectional fibres surrounding the defect.

The fibre volume fraction, V_f , distributions are determined using an image segmentation procedure followed by a local averaging filter as presented in [10]. The method segments the image into three material phases: fibres, matrix and the boundary between them. The segmentation is based on image

(a) Cross-section Z1 with submerged AFBD with fibres surrounding the defect. Through-thickness fibre orientation, ϕ_{xy} , is introduced at a point below the defect.

(b) Cross-section Z2 at the central location of the AFBD with the defect located at the profile surface.

Figure 3: LFOV grayscale micrographs from cross-sections presented in Figure 1b

Figure 4: Fibre distribution estimated for cross-section Z1 in Figure 1b. (Left) Through-thickness fibre orientation distribution, ϕ_{xy} . (Right) Fibre volume fraction distribution, V_f , estimated with a kernel size of $10 \times D_f$. Field quantities inside the defect area are masked and treated differently in the FE-model.

thresholding, where the material phases are separated by two thresholds determined from the grayscale distribution and a predetermined average fibre volume fraction, \bar{V}_f . The segmented image is semi-binary, with matrix and fibre pixels equal to 0 and 1, respectively, while the boundary phase pixels act as a ramping function between 0 and 1. As the compressive strength predictions are based on homogenised material properties, an averaging filter is applied to the semi-binary image, using a square kernel size related to the fibre diameter, $D_f \approx 7 \mu\text{m}$.

The resulting V_f distribution for cross-section Z1 is presented in Figure 4, for the right half of the image. Similar to the estimated orientations, the defect area has been masked in the estimation of the V_f distribution. The input \bar{V}_f used for the method is usually characterised from a burn-off test of the pristine material. However, as presented in [9], the local V_f surrounding the AFBD is deviating significantly from the burn-off test, where the pristine $\bar{V}_f = 0.67$ cannot be used directly. Instead, \bar{V}_f is estimated for the unidirectional fibres surrounding the defect using Otsu's thresholding, and used as input for the three-phase image segmentation procedure [10].

The material state within the masked defect area presented in Figure 4 is treated differently from surrounding unidirectional fibres. A random fibre orientation distribution with a low \bar{V}_f is assumed, and material properties are considered homogeneous and isotropic in the FE-model presented in the following.

4.2 Finite element model

A 2D plane strain FE-model is created in the commercial software AbaqusTM. The model resembles the sandwich beam and four-point bending setup in Figure 2. The beam model presented in Figure 5 is created as a single part, with material properties assigned to partitioned sets constituting the different materials described in Section 4.4. The beam is subjected to four-point bending, where the support and load rollers are included as rigid analytical solids. Surface-to-surface contact with the finite sliding formulation is imposed between the beam and rollers. The left support roller is replaced by a fixed boundary condition to stabilise initial contact and lock rigid body motions. The other support roller is fixed while a vertical displacement is applied to the load rollers, during a non-linear static step using the

Figure 5: 2D plane strain FE-model of sandwich beam in a four-point bending configuration. (Zoomed view) A high-resolution mesh is used to import image data in the dashed black square with an illustration of the AFB. Mesh transition between the yellow and black dashed squares with element sizes from $10 \times D_f \rightarrow T_{FS}/4$, where T_{FS} is the face sheet thickness. Blue line segments on the tension and compression side are used for calculating far-field strain presented in Section 5.

Riks arc-length method for capturing non-linear material behaviour.

The material model used for predicting compressive failure is based on homogenised material properties that do not include a length scale, and as a result, is highly mesh dependent. To mimic the length scale associated with kink band formation, the element size presented in the zoomed image in Figure 5 is related to a typical kink band width of $\approx 10 \times D_f$ as observed in the literature [14]. Computational time is reduced by assigning a coarse mesh to regions surrounding the defect with an element size equal to 1.25×2.5 mm. The decision to create the beam as a single part was to avoid tie constraints between dissimilar meshes, which can potentially cause convergence issues in the FE solver. To circumvent this issue, a transition from small to large elements is generated using a partitioning strategy as demonstrated between the black and yellow dashed lines. Far field strain is calculated using element node coordinates along the blue line segment on the face sheet surface, and compared with experimentally measured values. Finally, the 2D beam model is based on the AbaqusTM solid 8-node plane strain element, *CPE8*, with 3×3 integration points and is discretised with a total of ≈ 40000 elements (≈ 32000 of those are in the fine resolution mesh).

4.3 Mapping field quantities to finite element model

The field quantities, fibre orientations and fibre volume fractions, determined from micrographs in Section 4.1, are mapped to the high-resolution mesh presented in Figure 5. Element integration points from the mesh are exported from AbaqusTM and superimposed onto the image data, where all integration points are assigned an orientation and fibre volume fraction according to their coordinates. This step results in a loss of spatial resolution from the image data to the mesh of $\approx 0.58 \mu\text{m} \rightarrow 26 \mu\text{m}$. To capture the average fibre distribution within an element, field quantities are averaged for each integration point in a region corresponding to their fractional coverage of the element area. In AbaqusTM, material orientations are updated at all integration points using the user-subroutine, *ORIENT*, where a transformation matrix, T , is defined according to through-thickness material orientations ϕ_{xy}

$$\mathbf{T}(\phi_{xy}) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi_{xy} & -\sin \phi_{xy} & 0 \\ \sin \phi_{xy} & \cos \phi_{xy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} . \quad (1)$$

Similarly, local V_f are updated at the integration points by the user-subroutine described in the following section.

4.4 Material properties and non-linear constitutive model

Material properties used in the FE-model are not disclosed due to confidentiality agreements; however, a brief introduction to the input properties is presented in the following and summarised in Table 2. Four sets of material properties are used in the beam model. The PMMA core is assigned isotropic linear-elastic properties with a stiffness, $E_{PMMA} \approx E_{UDCFPP}^C/50$, where E_{UDCFPP}^C is the uniaxial compressive stiffness of the UDCFPP.

The material properties used for the face sheets are defined for three distinct regions. Properties for the fuzz ball defect are based on the observations presented in Section 4.1, where the fibre orientation can be considered somewhat random, with a low \bar{V}_f . To account for the local distribution within the fuzz ball, material properties are assumed isotropic linear-elastic with a fibre volume fraction estimated from the image ($\bar{V}_f \approx 0.49$), and calculated using the combined rule of mixtures for random fibre orientation distributions [15], resulting in a stiffness, $E_{Fuzz} \approx E_{UDCFPP}^C/4$.

The pristine material properties of the UDCFPP are based on observations from the experimental campaign in [9], which indicates linear-elastic behaviour within the tested failure strain level of the UDCFPP far from the defect area. Furthermore, it is highlighted that the stiffness of the UDCFPP is different in tension and compression. Material properties are thus assigned to the UDCFPP face sheets relative to the beam's neutral axis. The UDCFPP on the tension side is included as a linear-elastic transversely isotropic material with a uniaxial stiffness, $E_{UDCFPP}^T = 1.05 \cdot E_{UDCFPP}^C$.

Table 2: Material properties and model assumptions related to the FE-model in Figure 5.

Material	Model
UDCFPP ^C	UMAT model with elastic-plastic material properties for the fibres and matrix [11]
UDCFPP ^T	Transverse isotropic linear-elastic material with $E_{UDCFPP}^T = 1.05 \cdot E_{UDCFPP}^C$
Fuzz ball	Isotropic linear-elastic material with $E_{Fuzz} \approx E_{UDCFPP}^C/4$
PMMA	Isotropic linear-elastic material with $E_{PMMA} \approx E_{UDCFPP}^C/50$

Material properties used for the UDCFPP on the compressive side of the beam reflect the compressive kink band failure mode observed from experiments. A non-linear constitutive model assuming a long-waved deformation pattern (kinking theory) is used to describe the elastic-plastic response of the UDCFPP [11], and is implemented in AbaqusTM through a User-defined Material model (UMAT). The material model is summarised in [10], and only some of the governing equations are presented here. The non-linear behaviour of the composite is described using a rate-dependent constitutive law, presented using index notation

$$\dot{t}_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \dot{u}_{l,k} \quad i, j, k, l = \{1, 2\} \quad , \quad (2)$$

where rates of nominal stresses, \dot{t}_{ij} , are related to spatial velocity gradients, $\dot{u}_{l,k}$, through a composite constitutive tensor, C_{ijkl} .

The constitutive tensor for the composite material is derived from the constitutive relation of the fibres and matrix material, assuming isotropic elastic-plastic material behaviour. The constituent properties are homogenised using the local fibre volume fraction and the *iso-strain* and *-stress* assumptions, where the fibres and matrix share a common stretching and rotation along the fibre direction, and transmit identical tractions across boundaries, respectively. The elastic-plastic behaviour of the fibre and matrix materials is characterised using simple uniaxial testing and implemented in the model using the Ramberg-Osgood equation

$$\varepsilon_{eq} = \frac{\sigma_{eq}}{E} + \frac{3}{7} \frac{\sigma^{RO}}{E} \left(\frac{\sigma_{eq}}{\sigma^{RO}} \right)^{n^{RO}} \quad , \quad (3)$$

where ε_{eq} and σ_{eq} are the equivalent strain and stress from the uniaxial test, E is the elastic modulus of the constituent measured in the strain range [0.05, 0.25]%, and σ^{RO} and n^{RO} are used for fitting the equation to the stress-strain results. Matrix properties are characterised from a tensile test. In contrast, the carbon fibre properties are back-calculated from a compression test of the pristine UDCFPP using the matrix properties and the fibre volume fraction as presented in [10]. The compressive strength is, thus, predicted solely based on the elastic-plastic material properties used for the non-linear constitutive model, and it does not require additional failure criteria parameters to predict the compressive strength.

5 Results and discussion

Results from the experimental campaign [9] are presented here and compared with numerical predictions. The test matrix in Table 1 includes five reference beams with the pristine UDCFPP. Results from the reference beams are omitted in this work, but can be found in [9], where it is shown that, despite a longer support span, all reference beams failed at the load rollers due to high indentation loads. Nevertheless, high strain levels were obtained for the reference beams and used here to normalise the results. The following strain-to-failure results may thus be regarded as failure strain relative to the pristine material.

In contrast to the reference beams, all beams with AFBs failed in the gauge section with two distinct failure events. These were characterised as damage initiation in the vicinity of the AFB, followed by complete compressive failure of the UDCFPP face sheet. Damage initiation appeared as a transverse crack perpendicular to the load direction and outside the boundary of the visible defect. The crack appeared at a location similar to cross-section Z1, in Figure 1, and was contained within the sample width until unstable compressive failure of the face sheet. For a more detailed account of the failure sequence with images showing all failure events, the reader is referred to [9].

A post-mortem analysis was conducted using optical microscopy of a cross-section similar to Z1. From Figure 6, a submerged AFB divides the fibres into two sections with substantial fibre misalignments on both sides. The highlighted region shows clear signs of kink band failure towards the free surface of the face sheet. A splitting crack extends from the kink band and separates the misaligned fibres from the AFB. The sequence of failure modes is unknown, but it is argued that the kink band failure precedes the splitting crack, as fibres were observed to shoot out of the surface after damage initiation. Kink band failure of the fibres towards the PMMA core was associated with complete failure of the face sheet.

Figure 6: Post-mortem micrograph of failed UDCFPP with an AFB at a cross-section similar to Z1 in Figure 1. An epoxy adhesive was injected into the failure zone before microscopy preparations. The figure is slightly altered from the one presented in [9].

Figure 7: Absolute shear strain components, $|\varepsilon_{12}|$, exported from the high-resolution FE mesh integration points, after compressive kink band failure. Zoomed view shows strain localisation at integration points with values above a shear strain threshold, $\varepsilon_{12 Threshold} = 2.5\%$.

Based on observations from the post-mortem analysis, it was concluded that damage initiation is a local failure event with a predominant through-thickness kink band failure plane. The conclusion suggested that damage initiation can be simplified to a 2D problem, and was the basis for choosing the 2D micrograph modelling approach. The two cross-sections presented in Figure 1 are used as input in the FE-model capable of predicting kink band failure; however, the splitting crack is not included due to the argument that kink band failure precedes crack propagation.

The predicted location of kink band failure is presented as strain localisation using shear strain components from the FE integration points. FE results are presented for the high-resolution mesh described in Section 4.2, while the full four-point bending model results are omitted. A scatter plot of the absolute shear strain, $|\varepsilon_{12}|$, for cross-section Z1 is presented in Figure 7. The associated colorbar is limited by a threshold strain, $\varepsilon_{12}^{Threshold}$, used to identify strain localisation, where integration points with strain values above the threshold are yellow. The zoomed box shows a region with strain localisation where integration point values are larger than the threshold. These integration points are plotted on top of the orientation distribution plot for the corresponding cross-section in Figure 8, and used to associate predicted kink band failure with the input fibre orientation distribution.

The kink band failure prediction for cross-section Z1, in Figure 8, is located above the AFBD towards the free surface. Strain localisation is observed at a thin section of fibres with large through-thickness initial misalignments up to $\phi_{xy} = 11^\circ$. The predicted failure location corresponds to the failure location observed experimentally for different samples in Figure 6.

Similarly, the predicted location of kink band failure for cross-section Z2 in Figure 9 is associated with large initial fibre misalignments below the AFBD ($\phi_{xy} \approx 15^\circ$). Figure 10 presents a zoomed view of the damage initiation regions, where individual integration points from the FE-models are clearly marked. The predicted kink bands initiate at the surface of the UDCFPP or the AFBD boundary, but do not fully propagate through the thickness before the arc-length FE-solver stalls due to excessive displacements. However, model predictions are used to quantify the compressive strength associated with limit load instability, which is successfully obtained for the presented model predictions.

The normalised load and strain results are presented for the AFBD beams and numerical predictions, in Figure 11. Experimental results are normalised with respect to the beam widths and compared to the unit-width plane strain FE-models. The constitutive response of the model predictions is in agreement with experimental results, only with a noticeable difference to the 40 mm wide beams. The difference in the experimental compliance is attributed to the difference in the defect-to-sample width ratio, where the wider specimens are less affected by the macroscopic defect in the centre of the gauge section. Furthermore, the 2D FE-models assume a constant defect throughout the width of the UDCFPP, and

Figure 8: Location of predicted kink band failure for cross-section Z1. Micrograph presented with fibre orientations distribution and integration point values from the FE-model. Strain localisation is plotted using integration point shear strain components above a threshold.

Figure 9: Location of predicted kink band failure for cross-section Z2. Integration points with shear strains above $\varepsilon_{12}^{Threshold} = 4\%$ are plotted on top of the orientation distribution.

Figure 10: Zoom images of predicted damage initiation regions.

should behave more similarly to the narrow 40 mm wide beams. However, the plane strain assumption in the FE-models results in a stiffer response and falls, in the current case, accidentally closer to the compliance of the 60 mm wide beams.

The normalised compressive strain to failure from experiments is 0.297 ± 0.032 (mean \pm st.dev.), while the numerical models predict 0.306 ± 0.001 , thus demonstrating only a 3% deviation from average experimental results. The failure strain predicted for cross-section Z2 is slightly higher than Z1, and with a different kink band failure location along the x-axis as seen in Figure 8 and 9. From the experimental observations in Figure 6, kink band failure of the surface fibres corresponds to the model prediction of cross-section Z1 with the lowest strain to failure. However, the predicted failure strains for the two cross-sections are close and suggest competing failure planes. Furthermore, from an experimental point of view, hidden damage in this area may have occurred simultaneously with the observed damage from the surface.

Figure 11: Normalised experimental and numerical load values plotted against normalised strain results. Results are normalised with respect to the mean failure load and strain from the pristine material [9]. Additionally, experimental results are normalised with respect to beam width. Far field strain is measured according to Figures 2 and 5.

5.1 Method limitations

The homogenised non-linear constitutive model used for simulating kink band failure lacks a length scale and is fundamentally mesh dependent. A length scale is implemented in the model by defining an element size equal to a kink band width observed from the literature. Strength predictions are sensitive to the chosen element size and should thus be related to experimental observations for the specific case. These were not obtained; however, the chosen element size resulted in a high prediction accuracy as presented in Section 5.

A direct consequence of the 2D simplification is the ability to fully describe the fibre distribution surrounding the defect. The presented method is based on the assumption of a characteristic failure plane, which, in reality, might not exist for this type of defect. Similarly, the fibre distribution within the embedded defect appears random in all three dimensions, but some structure from the carbon fibre rovings remains. As discussed in Section 4.1, the 2D approach results in orientation artefacts with large through-thickness orientations, ultimately leading to failure predictions within the defect, which was not observed experimentally. For this reason, the fibre distribution within the AFBD was idealised as an isotropic material. 3D modelling based on X-ray computed tomography data is required to circumvent these assumptions, but comes with long acquisition times and a significant computational cost.

6 Summary and conclusion

The challenge of predicting the compressive strength of unidirectional fibre-reinforced polymers with manufacturing-induced defects is considered in this work. The risk of structural damage or complete failure in large composite structures is strongly related to fibre misalignment defects in the main load-carrying components. An image-based finite element model was developed to predict the compressive strength based on micrographs of fibre-misalignment defects. Fuzz ball defects in fibre-reinforced pultruded profiles were considered in this study. A four-point bending test of a sandwich beam with pultruded profiles as face sheets was used to successfully quantify a compressive strain to failure reduction of 71 % relative to the pristine material. Compressive failure was found to be localised kink band failure of fibres surrounding the submerged defect, where failure appeared 2-dimensional. The observations inspired the finite element modelling approach using micrographs and a non-linear constitutive model capable of predicting kink band failure.

A finite element model resembling the experimental four-point bending test setup was developed, where two micrographs of the same defect were used to predict the compressive strength in the gauge section. Fibre distributions were determined from the micrographs and represented using fibre orientations and fibre volume fractions, which were subsequently used as input for the finite element model.

The four-point bending model's constitutive response agreed with the experimental results, with compressive failure strain predictions within 3 % of the experimentally measured average failure strain. The predicted compressive strain to failure reduction is thus equivalent to the experimental measurements, and the 2D FE-modelling approach based on micrographs was found to be sufficiently accurate for characterising the detrimental effect of manufacturing-induced defects. Thus, the proposed method can predict compressive failure of fibre misalignment defects, with accurate predictions for failure location and strengths. It may therefore be used to investigate realistic manufacturing-induced defects to define acceptable limits for different defect characteristics.

References

- [1] Mishnaevsky L 2022 *MATERIALS* **15**. doi:10.3390/ma15092959
- [2] Nelson J W, Riddle T W and Cairns D S 2017 *WIND ENERGY SCI* **2** 641–652. doi:10.5194/wes-2-641-2017
- [3] Wilhelmsson D, Gutkin R, Edgren F and Asp L 2018 *COMPOS PART A-APPL S* **107** 665–674. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2018.02.013
- [4] Davidson P and Waas A M 2017 *COMPOS STRUCT* **176** 582–596. doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2017.05.046
- [5] Ennis B L, Das S and Norris R E 2023 *COMPOS PART B-ENG* **265**. doi:10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.110960
- [6] Shaw-Stewart D and Sumerak J E 2000 *2 - The pultrusion process* (Woodhead Publishing) ISBN 978-1-85573-425-8

- [7] Jeppesen N, Mikkelsen L P, Dahl A B, Christensen A N and Dahl V A 2021 *COMPOS PART A-APPL S* **149**(July) 106541. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2021.106541
- [8] Wilhelmsson D, Talreja R, Gutkin R and Asp L E 2019 *COMPOS SCI TECHNOL* **181**. doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2019.107685
- [9] Ferguson O V, Rifai J, Wisnom M R, Jørgensen J B and Mikkelsen L P 2025 *COMPOS PART A-APPL S* 109059. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2025.109059
- [10] Ferguson O V, Jørgensen J B and Mikkelsen L P 2025 Compressive strength predictions for carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profiles: Imaging modalities for quantifying the detrimental effect of fibre misalignments - Submitted for review
- [11] Christoffersen J and Myhre Jensen H 1996 *MECH MATER* **24** 305–315. doi:10.1016/S0167-6636(96)00052-X
- [12] Wu X and Wisnom M R 2023 *COMPOS STRUCT* **304**. doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2022.116467
- [13] Jeppesen N, Dahl V A, Christensen A N, Dahl A B and Mikkelsen L P 2020 *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* vol 942. doi:10.1088/1757-899X/942/1/012037
- [14] Budiansky B and Fleck N 1993 *J MECH PHYS SOLIDS* **41**(1) 183–211. doi:10.1016/0022-5096(93)90068-Q
- [15] Krenchel H 1964 *Fibre Reinforcement: Theoretical and Practical Investigations of the Elasticity and Strength of Fibre-reinforced Materials* (Akademisk forlag)